

2nd TwiNSol-CECs Workshop

Advanced Water Treatments in Emerging Contaminants Mitigation with Cutting-Edge Technologies

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia, 6-7 June 2024

CERTIFICATE

Djordja Kerkez

participated in the 2nd TwiNSol-CECs Workshop, an event organized within TwiNSol-CECs project by the Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, funded by EU (GA 101059867), and presented the invited lecture:

SLUDGE APPLICATION ON LAND: OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES

by Djurdja Kerkez, Milena Bečelić–Tomin, Anita Leovac Maćerak, Dragana Tomašević
Pilipović, Dejan Krčmar, Nataša Slijepčević, Vesna Pešić

In Novi Sad, June 7, 2024

Zita Šereš
2nd TwiNSol-CECs Workshop Chair

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Advanced Water Treatments in Emerging Contaminants Mitigation
with Cutting-Edge Technologies

Book of Abstracts

University of Novi Sad
Faculty of Technology Novi Sad
Novi Sad, Serbia

6 - 7 June 2024

2nd TwiNSol-CECs Workshop
*Advanced Water Treatments in Emerging Contaminants
Mitigation with Cutting-Edge Technologies*

Funded by the
European Union

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad,
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BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

2nd TwiNSol-CECs Workshop

**Advanced Water Treatments in Emerging Contaminants
Mitigation with Cutting-Edge Technologies**

**University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad (TFNS), Novi Sad, Serbia,
June 6-7, 2024**

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad,
Novi Sad, Serbia, 6-7 June 2024

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Dear colleagues, participants of the 2nd TwiNSol-CECs Workshop,

On behalf of the TwiNSol-CECs team, I am delighted to welcome you all to our 2nd Workshop with title "Advanced Water Treatments in Emerging Contaminants Mitigation with Cutting-Edge Technologies" organized in the frame of TwiNSol-CECs project (GA 101059867). We deeply appreciate your contributions in the form of oral and poster presentations, with the abstracts and full papers compiled in the Book of Abstracts and Proceedings, available on our project website (www.twinsol-cecs.com). We are really proud in securing this project under Horizon Europe patronage and are honored by the opportunities such as this event, enabled through execution of TwiNSol-CECs, to share knowledge and exchange ideas within the environmental research with colleagues from Serbia, Western Balkans, and EU.

This event aims to bring together scientists and experts focused on, but not limited to, the issues on removal of contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) from water by innovative technologies. Since „Cutting-Edge Technologies” in water treatment are part of our focus in TwinSol-CECs project, the 2nd Workshop highlights three key innovative technologies: membrane processes, advanced oxidation, and biosorption. Each of these technologies offers unique and effective approach for removing micropollutants and contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) from water. These innovative technologies, each with its distinct advantages, represent significant advancements in our quest for clean and safe water. By integrating these methods, we can develop more comprehensive and effective strategies for managing water quality and protecting public health.

Beyond these topics, the Workshop also acts as a forum for exchanging research ideas, exploration of complementarities and possibilities for collaboration, contributing to the harmonization of research and innovation efforts crucial for the sustainable transition envisioned by the Horizon Europe and Green Deal calls towards a zero-pollution, toxic-free environment.

The TwiNSol-CECs team wishes you a pleasant stay in Novi Sad and looks forward to engaging discussions on new research ideas and collaborative efforts towards a zero-pollution future,

Prof. Zita Šereš
Chair

2nd TwiNSol-CECs Workshop

Advanced Water Treatments in Emerging Contaminants Mitigation with Cutting-Edge Technologies

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Serbia
June 6-7, 2024

Agenda

Thursday – 6 June 2024

Morning session, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Blue Hall
(Chairs: Vanessa J. Pereira and Zita Šereš)

- 9:00 – 10:00 Registration (Entrance Hall of TFNS)
- 10:00 – 10:15 Official opening, Biljana Pajin, Dean of the Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, and Zita Šereš, Chair of the Workshop
- Plenary lectures (30 min per lecture + 5 min for Q&A after each lecture):*
- 10:15 – 10:50 João G. Crespo, Sylwin Pawlowski, Svetlozar Velizarov – **Ion-Exchange Membrane Processes: Perspectives in Water Treatment and Desalination**
- 10:50 – 11:25 Olívia Salomé G. P. Soares – **Catalytic advanced oxidation processes for pollutants degradation**
- 11:25 – 11:55 *Coffee break*
- Invited lectures (15 min per lecture + 5 min for Q&A after each lecture):*
- 11:55 – 12:15 Sanja Panić, Mirjana Petronijević, Igor Antić, Jelena Živančev, Maja Buljovčić, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović – **Heteroatom-doped pyrochar for efficient metal-free catalytic oxidation of contaminants of emerging concern**
- 12:15 – 12:35 Minja M. Bogunović, Ivana I. Ivančev-Tumbas – **Hybrid adsorption/membrane filtration in water treatment for the removal of organic micropollutants**
- 12:35 – 12:55 Nandor Nemestothy, Merve Visnyei, Veronika Kalauz-Simon, Peter Bakonyi – **Gaseous Byproducts in Wastewater Treatment: Challenges and Opportunities with Membrane Technology**
- 13:00 – 14:00 *Lunch*
- 14:00 – 14:30 *Poster session with Coffee*

Afternoon session, Faculty of Technology Blue Hall

(Chairs: Nandor Nemestothy and Nikola Maravić)

Invited lectures (15 min per lecture + 5 min for Q&A after each lecture):

- 14:30 – 14:50 Snežana Maletić, Jelena Beljin, Irina Jevrosimov, Tamara Apostolović, Srđan Rončević, Marijana Kragulj Isakovski – **The contribution of inoculated biochar to pesticide adsorption and biosorption**
- 14:50 – 15:10 Djurdja V. Kerkez, Milena R. Bečelić-Tomin, Anita S. Leovac Mačerak, Dragana D. Tomašević Pilipović, Dejan Krčmar, Nataša S. Slijepčević, Vesna Z. Pešić – **Sludge application on land: Opportunities and challenge**

Oral presentations (10 min per lecture + 5 min for Q&A after each lecture):

- 15:10 – 15:25 Szabolcs Kertész, Imre Vajk Fazekas, Martin Trancsik, Aws N. Al-Tayawi, József Richárd Lennert, Sándor Beszédes, József Csanádi, Tamás Szabó, Cecilia Hodúr, Gábor Veréb, Zsuzsanna László – **Enhancing the efficiency of low-pressure membrane separations using 3d printed spacers**
- 15:25 – 15:40 Aws N. Al-Tayawi, Hajnalka Csott, Nikolett Sz. Gulyás, József Richárd Lennert, Zsuzsanna Horváth Hovorka, Zsuzsanna László, Cecilia Hodúr, Szabolcs Kertész – **Evaluation of flow dynamics utilizing integrated 3d printed turbulence promoters for mitigation of membrane fouling**
- 15:40 – 15:55 Jelena Molnar Jazić, Tajana Simetić, Marijana Kragulj Isakovski, Aleksandra Tubić, Jasmina Agbaba – **Advanced oxidation processes for natural organic matter and emerging contaminants abatement in water treatment**
- 15:55 – 16:10 Jasmina Nikić, Malcolm A. Watson, Maja Vujić, Jovana Pešić, Jovana Jokić-Govedarica, Srđan Rončević, Jasmina Agbaba – **Addressing arsenic contamination: a polymer-based nanocomposite for water treatment**

Friday – 7 June 2024

Morning session, Faculty of Technology Blue Hall

(Chairs: João G. Crespo and Szabolcs Kertész)

- 9:00 – 10:00 Registration (Entrance Hall of TFNS)

Plenary lectures (30 min per lecture + 5 min for Q&A after each lecture):

- 10:00 – 10:30 Maria B. Cristóvão, Jorge Bernardo, Andreia Bento-Silva, Maria R. Bronze, João G. Crespo, Vanessa J. Pereira – **Mitigating Anticancer Drug Pollution: Nanofiltration for Control of Emerging Contaminants in Wastewater Effluents**

SLUDGE APPLICATION ON LAND: OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES

***Djurđa V. Kerkez**, Milena R. Bečelić–Tomin, Anita S. Leovac Maćerak, Dragana D. Tomašević Pilipović, Dejan Krčmar, Nataša S. Slijepčević, Vesna Z. Pešić**

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The concept of a circular economy implies a new approach to traditional wastewater treatment plants that is promoted to address important sustainability segments such as emissions, chemical consumption, water and energy interdependence and increasing amounts of post-treatment residues or bio-solids. Sludge is an organic substrate relatively rich in nutrients (nitrogen and phosphorus), as well as trace elements. The composition of sludge varies regionally and seasonally, but in general there is little monitoring of data on the content of nutrients in it. It is estimated that about 2.3-3.1 Mt of nitrogen and about 0.23 Mt of phosphorus are found in the sludge generated during one year in the world. Sludge produced from treatment of domestic sewage has long been applied to agriculture as a source of nutrients to displace mineral fertilizers.

In this research, excessive literature review was performed to access the sludge management practices in Europe. In addition, nutrient potential in sludge was evaluated on a national level. Major opportunities and challenges were identified.

27% of produced sludge in Europe is used in agriculture as fertilizer on arable land and pastures. This method is dominant in Bulgaria, Croatia, the Czech Republic, Denmark, Ireland, Lithuania, Norway, Spain and Sweden. Composting and similar uses: use of waste sludge after mixing with other organic material and composting, followed by use for parks and gardens takes about 21%. This method is dominant in Cyprus, Estonia, France, Hungary, Luxembourg and Slovakia. According to national sludge management program, in Republic of Serbia around 135 000 tons of dry mater of sludge can be expected in the future. This represents the source of nitrogen and phosphorus in amount of over 4500 tons each.

On the other hand, concerns arise from the possibility of the presence of various emerging contaminants. However, these risks should be viewed rationally in relation to the characteristics of the wastewater entering the plant, as well as through the efficiency and type of applied technologies in the water line, which is closely related to the quality of the separated sludge. By controlling the users of the sewage system and optimizing the operation of the wastewater treatment plant, these risks can be reduced to a minimum. Furthermore, more efficient technologies to preserve extract and reuse nutrients from sewage sludge can be used.

Finally, states need to recognize the real value of wastewater and the potential resources that can be recovered from it. They must include resource recovery and general circular economy principles in their strategies, investment planning and infrastructure design.

Keywords: Sludge management, Biosolids, Nutrients, Resource recovery, Circular economy

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